

Remember. The Children of Bullenhusser Damm

Developed by: Paintbucket Games

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Keywords

Death, Democratic Values, Empathy, Memorials, Political Science, Remembrance Culture, World War II History

Figure 1. *Remember. The Children of Bullenhusser Damm* in use by a student—image courtesy of Stiftung Hamburger Gedenkstätten (photographer: Iris Groschek).

Figure 2. Official key visual of *Remember. The Children of Bullenhusser Damm*. © Paintbucket Games.

Introduction

The digital remembrance game *Remember. The Children of Bullenhuser Damm* is based on the history of the Bullenhuser Damm Memorial in Hamburg, which commemorates 20 Jewish children and 28 adults murdered by the SS in 1945. Before their murder, the children were subjected to pseudo-medical experiments at the Neuengamme concentration camp. The game introduces young people to the memorial's history, focusing not on the crime but on remembrance culture and the question, "How is this history relevant to me today?" Players experience different perspectives on remembrance through the eyes of five students from the school Bullenhuser Damm in the late 1970s. They uncover traces that reveal the background to this unimaginable crime. The game complements visits to the memorial, encourages reflection, and promotes active participation in remembrance culture.

The game was developed by the Foundation of Hamburg Memorials and Learning Centers Commemorating the Victims of Nazi Crimes, in collaboration with Paintbucket Games, and funded by the Alfred Landecker Foundation. The Oldenburg Gamelab developed teaching instructions. The game is available for free on both Android and iOS platforms.

Facts

Release date: 28 November 2024 (German version); 14 April 2025 (English version)

Developer: Paintbucket Games

Game type: Digital

Number of players: Single player

Format: Hybrid; In class, all students play the game simultaneously, but each student participates individually.

Time frame: Each of the five individual character stories has a duration of approximately 20 to 30 minutes. In class, students may select a character from among the characters, with each student typically playing one. To experience all five characters, the total gameplay time is 2 hours.

Languages: English, German

Environment: The game is available for free download on Android, iOS, and macOS.

System Requirements: Android 9 or later, iOS 14.0 or later, macOS 11.0 or later. For optimal use, the game is best played on tablets, allowing each student to engage individually and subsequently participate in group discussions. Content rating: USK 12+ (contains themes of violence and war).

Material: The game can be integrated into classroom instruction and played without additional materials. However, to support effective implementation, comprehensive teaching instructions have been developed, offering teachers lesson plans and supplementary source material. Instructional resources are available on the memorial's website.

Materials have been tested in history classes and are designed to be user-friendly for educators.

Price: The game is free on Android, iOS, and macOS. Teaching materials are also available at no cost, in hard copy or electronic format, on the memorial's website.

Resonance & Criticism

Students who engaged with the game, whether at school, university, or directly at the memorial, responded very positively. They participated in meaningful discussions about remembrance, personal impact, and responsibility. This real-life connection is a key reason for incorporating games into educational settings. In "Remember. The Children of Bullenhuser Damm," this connection is tangible: young people interact with the characters, identify with them, and reflect deeply – an outcome rarely achieved so directly in the classroom. As a result, the game is well-suited to both history and civic education. It has received very positive press coverage and, in 2025, was nominated for 'Best Serious Game' at the German Computer Game Award (DCP).

Game Principle & Process

The game immerses players in the roles of students at Bullenhuser Damm School c. 1980, who uncover traces of the Nazi past and are prompted to reflect on history and memory. Using a point-and-click interface, players interact with various characters and explore different time periods, gradually constructing a personal, subjective narrative of remembrance. Remembrance is depicted as fragmented, inconsistent, and individual, thereby highlighting the multiplicity of perspectives.

Each of the five playable characters embodies distinct memories and themes, all of which are connected to the story of the children of Bullenhuser Damm. These diverse themes enable players of different ages to explore a range of topics and foster meaningful conversations.

The memorial's context is introduced at the outset; however, players must actively uncover the historical background through exploration. They visit multiple locations, interact with people, and collect objects, which together form "memory spaces" enriched with original documents, audio recordings, and eyewitness accounts. Learning unfolds gradually, mirroring the processes inherent in real-life remembrance work, and the central message remains that such atrocities must never be repeated. Designed for both individual and group play, this adventure game encourages discussion and emotional engagement, ensuring that students are supported and given a voice. The interactive format facilitates trial-and-error, reflection, and a sense of self-efficacy, thereby addressing a range of competencies. Most importantly, the game motivates young people to connect historical reflection with their own lives and present-day experiences.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The game is well-suited for teaching history lessons on National Socialism, the Holocaust, and remembrance culture. It can be integrated into a variety of subjects, including history, politics, religion, ethics, or as part of an independent project. Central to the game are the questions ‘What is remembrance?’ and ‘How does this relate to me?’, which are aimed at fostering an understanding of the significance of remembrance culture and memorial sites, as well as encouraging personal reflection on one’s own role and responsibility in the remembrance process. Additionally, the game can be used to prepare for or follow up on a visit to the memorial site.

Teachers are responsible for providing students with foundational knowledge of Nazi Germany and the Holocaust, framing the use of the game, and ensuring that the gaming session is structured and purposeful. Comprehensive teaching instructions, including lesson plans and supplementary materials, are available to support reflection on the question “What does it mean to remember Nazi crimes?” These materials have been tested in educational settings. The game is recommended for students aged 12 and older, as it aligns with curricular requirements and students’ prior knowledge.

The game’s straightforward mechanics make it accessible and easy for both students and teachers to engage with. It is advisable for teachers to play through the game in advance of classroom use. Students may play the game simultaneously on tablets, with gameplay followed by group and plenary discussions. At the conclusion of each story, a “memory room” links the digital experience to authentic sources and eyewitness interviews, creating a powerful moment of realization for students as digital narratives merge with real historical accounts. While the game offers a complete narrative, it intentionally leaves many questions unanswered, underscoring the idea that remembrance is an ongoing process and never fully concluded.

Effectiveness

During development, the game was evaluated by several focus groups comprising 20–30 students from various schools, grade levels (7–13), and school types. Feedback from both teachers and students was actively incorporated into the design process. Students played the game both at school and at the memorial site. The game proved highly immersive, with students strongly identifying with the teenage characters and actively engaging in the search for clues. Testing demonstrated that the game successfully engaged all students. The educational impact was particularly profound when the game was played on-site, immediately before visiting the memorial.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game introduces the fate of the murdered children with sensitivity and respect; however, the narrative and the visit to the authentic site may evoke feelings of grief or shock. The game

is designed to support players in discussing the crime and processing their emotions. Teachers should be aware that both students and the educators themselves may have emotional responses, making thorough preparation and follow-up essential. Nevertheless, evaluations have shown that students valued the opportunity to learn about the children through the game before visiting the memorial or engaging more deeply with the historical events.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Dave Calgren

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